

Fraction I : It responded to positive Libermann-Burchard and Salkowski reactions indicating the presence of steroidal nucleus. Co-TLC with authentic samples employing n-hexane : ethyl acetate (5 : 1)^a and benzene : ethyl acetate (4 : 1)⁴ ascertained the presence of stigmaterol and β -sitosterol in this fraction.

Fraction II : It gave positive Molisch's test besides usual tests for sterol. It was crystallised from chloroform : methanol to colourless flakes (m.p. 290° ; lit m.p. 292°)⁵. Elemental analysis showed C, 73.56% ; H, 9.88% (required C, 73.17% ; H, 10.10% for C₂₈H₄₈O₆).

It was characterised as α -spinasterol 3-glucoside by infrared studies.

Co-TLC, Co-IR studies and the preparation of derivatives of aglycone further supported the identification.

Fraction III : It was found to have two flavonoidal aglycones by paper and thin layer chromatography. Separation by borax-complex formation method yielded kaempferol 12 mg (m.p. 276-8° ; lit. m.p. 279°)⁶ ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 267, 366 (sh), 367 nm and quercetin 15 mg (m.p. 310° ; lit. m.p. 316°)⁶ ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 256, 269 (sh), 300 (sh), 368 nm.

The identities were further confirmed by Co-chromatography, Co-UV studies with the authentic samples and derivative preparation.

Flavonoidal substance from *fraction IV* was isolated by precipitation with basic lead acetate and was characterised as rutin 60 mg (m.p. 190-1° ; lit. m.p. 188-190°) ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 257, 268 (sh), 295 (sh) ; 360 nm.

Undepressed mixed melting point, Co-chromatography and Co-UV studies further supported the identification.

References

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Second Order Beckmann Rearrangement of 3 β -chloro-19-nor-5-methyl-5 β -cholest-9 (10)-en-6-one Oxime

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IN continuation of reports on azasteroids^{1,2}, we subjected compound(II) to Beckmann rearrangement which provided single nitrile (III). The product (III) on base hydrolysis resulted into dehydrohalogenated compound(IV). The structures of (III) and (IV) have been established on the basis of elemental and spectral evidences.

The ketone (I), (m.p. 63-64°) was prepared according to the procedure described by Aebli *et al.*³ and was converted by the general oximation method⁴ to its oxime (II), crystallized from ethanol m.p. 135° (positive Beilstein test), (Found : C, 74.79 ; H, 10.21 ; N, 3.35. C₂₇H₄₄ONCl requires C, 74.82 H, 10.16 ; N, 3.23%). IR spectrum gave peaks at 3220 (OH), 1670 (C=N-OH) and 745 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The n.m.r. spectrum of (II) exhibited signals at 9.2br,s (OH, disappeared on addition of D₂O), 4.4m (C3- α H, W_{1/2}=9 Hz), 1.5s (C5-CH₃), 0.9 and 0.8 (other methyls).

The oxime (II) (500 mg) on treatment with thionyl chloride (10 ml) at -20° followed by treatment with an excess of 4N KOH (25 ml) afforded a sticky coloured material, which on passing through neutral alumina gave 3 β -chloro-5, 6-secocholesta-19-nor-9(10), 5(19)-dien-6-onitrile (III) as a noncrystallizable oil (150 mg). The homogeneity of the oily product(III) was checked by TLC. The nitrile(III) gave positive Beilstein test, (Found : C, 77.89 ; H, 10.12 ; N, 3.50. C₂₇H₄₂ClN requires C, 78.07 ; H, 10.12 ; N, 3.37%). The i.r. spectrum showed bands at 2240 (C \equiv N), 1630 (C=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The n.m.r. spectrum gave a broadened singlet at δ 5.42 which is easily ascribable for =C19-H₂ (vinylic methylene protons). A broad multiplet for C3-proton was observed at δ 4.25 (C3- α H, W_{1/2}=16 Hz). Other signals were seen at δ 0.91, 0.81 and 0.68 (other methyls). The u.v. spectrum of (III) gave absorption maxima at 215 nm which proves the presence of diene system.

The oxime (II) (500 mg) was treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (500 mg) and pyridine (4 ml) in the usual manner. After work up and passing through neutral alumina gave (III) (TLC, IR and

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NOTES

NMR identical with the sample obtained using SOCl_2).

The nitrile (III) (100 mg) on hydrolysis with 2% methanolic KOH (10 ml) and usual work up procedure gave 5,6-secocholesta-19-nor-3(4), 5(19), 9(10)-trien-6-onitrile (IV) as an oil (60 mg), (Found: C, 84.98; H, 10.91; N, 3.52. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{41}\text{N}$ requires C, 85.48; H, 10.81; N, 3.69%). In i.r. spectrum bands were observed at 2240 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1635cm^{-1}

C
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(-C=C-C-C=C-). The n.m.r. spectrum showed a broad unresolved multiplet centred at δ 5.63 ascribable for 4-vinylic protons (C3-1H, C4-1H, =C19-H₂), δ 0.71 (C13-CH₃), 0.93 and 0.83 (other methyls). U. V. shows the absorption maxima at 270 nm which also confirmed the extension of conjugation of diene.

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